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WDR19 is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.

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We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery/identification of WDR19 as a zygotic cell factor required or important during the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

Citations

1. Bredrup, C., Saunier, S., Oud, M.M., Fiskerstrand, T., Hoischen, A., Brackman, D., Leh, S.M., Midtbø, M., Filhol, E., Bole-Feysot, C. and Nitschké, P., 2011. Ciliopathies with skeletal anomalies and renal insufficiency due to mutations in the IFT-A gene WDR19. *The American Journal of Human Genetics*, 89(5), pp.634-643.